

Psychiatric Comorbidity and Quality of Life in Individuals with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: A Cross-Sectional StudyShubham Sharma¹, Siddharth Dixit², Rajesh Agrawal³, Arpit Jaiswal⁴¹Junior Resident, Department of Psychiatry, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India²Professor and Head, Department of Psychiatry, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India³Professor and Head, Department of Respiratory Medicine, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract:

Background: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a prevalent, preventable, and treatable condition marked by persistent and progressive airflow limitation, stemming from an enhanced chronic inflammatory response of the airways and lungs to harmful particles and gases. Individuals with COPD are susceptible to psychiatric disorders that significantly impact their morbidity. This study aimed to assess the psychiatric comorbidity and quality of life among individuals with COPD, addressing the notable gap in Indian literature on this subject.

Aim: To estimate the prevalence of psychiatric comorbidity and assess the quality of life in individuals with COPD.

Material and Methods: 140 patients identified with COPD were categorized as per the severity according to the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) criteria by the pulmonary medicine consultant. Subsequently, patients were referred from the Pulmonary Medicine Department to the Psychiatry OPD for further evaluation. A semi-structured interview was used to collect socio-demographic and clinical data. Upon consenting, patients underwent a comprehensive history taking and physical examination conducted by a resident psychiatrist. The Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) was employed to identify psychiatric comorbidities. The Quality of Life (QOL) of the patients was assessed using the World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL-BREF) questionnaire. The data was statistically analyzed using SPSS software version 23.0. A p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: Patients constituted 42.9% (n=60) in GOLD 1, 45% (n=63) in GOLD 2 and 12.7% (n=17) in GOLD 3 stage. Psychiatric comorbidity was noted in 65.7% of the sample, with varying prevalence across GOLD stages: 26.7% in GOLD1, 93.7% in GOLD2, and 100% GOLD3. Among these comorbidities, the frequency for major depressive episode affecting 36.9% of patients was the highest followed by generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) 21.7%, panic disorder 17.3%, and dysthymia 3.2%. Quality of life scores declined significantly with increasing COPD severity. The mean scores in physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment domains were 45.14±11.98, 44.86±10.86, 49.39±11.64, and 51.10±11.22, respectively. A significant correlation was found between psychiatric comorbidity and poorer quality of life (p<0.001).

Conclusion: These results highlight the wide-ranging effects of COPD, which include respiratory health as well as physical, mental, and social well-being. It is essential to use a holistic approach to therapy, which includes patient education, psychological support, early identification, prevention, and thorough treatment techniques.

Keywords: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, Psychiatric comorbidity, Quality of life.

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Introduction

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a common preventable and treatable disease characterized by persistent and progressive airflow limitation that is caused due to enhanced chronic inflammatory response of the airways and lungs to

noxious particles and gases. [1] COPD is a spectrum of airway diseases, on the one end of which is chronic bronchitis while the other end belongs to emphysema. The global prevalence of physiologically defined chronic obstructive pulmonary dis-

ease in adults aged ≥ 40 years is approximately 9-10 per cent. [2] It has been discovered that the chronic nature of this condition affects this population's ability to operate on a daily basis, making them more susceptible to psychiatric disorders, which in turn raises the morbidity rate of COPD. Quality of Life is known to be a significant determinant for measuring the impact of chronic disease on patients [3] & was therefore found to be impaired due to COPD thus preventing people with the condition from socializing and enjoying their hobbies. More recently, some reviews have highlighted the negative impact of psychological comorbidity on Health-related Quality of Life (HRQoL) of COPD patients and found an association between psychological impairment manifesting with psychiatric comorbidities and worsening of respiratory-specific HRQoL, independent of COPD severity. [4,5] The etiology between COPD and psychiatric comorbidity continues to be complex & likely bidirectional and there has been limited investigation into this topic in India. Hence the study was conducted as there was scarcity of Indian literature on this subject.

Material and Methods

The study was conducted at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh on OPD and IPD basis. It was an observational study and conducted over a period of one year. Inclusion criteria included patients in the age group of 30-80 years and all participants being diagnosed by the pulmonary medicine consultant as COPD and being referred to Psychiatry OPD. All patients who fulfilled their respective inclusion and exclusion criteria were included in the study. 140 COPD patients were studied according to sample size formula for cross-sectional study in finite population. A semi structured form was specifically designed for recording information including person's name, age, sex, education, marital status, religion, occupation, state, socioeconomic status, and the type of family and took around 5-10 minutes to fill.

Patients provided written informed consent before participation. Following this patients were assessed for psychiatric disorders using the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI), which is designed as a brief structured diagnostic interview for the major psychiatric disorders in DSM-III-R, DSM-IV, DSM-V and ICD-10. Validation and reliability studies done comparing the MINI to the SCID-P for DSM-III-R and the Composite International Diagnostic Interview showed that the MINI had similar reliability and validity properties when

compared to both these instruments but can be administered in a much shorter period of time that is around 15 minutes. [6] The standard MINI assesses the 17 most common psychiatric disorders. Questions are phrased to allow only "yes" or "no" answers. Subsequently, the Quality of Life (QOL) [11] of patients was evaluated using the World Health Organization Quality of Life (WHOQOL) questionnaire. [7] The WHOQOL was created as a thorough evaluation instrument to gauge a person's quality of life in a number of areas. It has strong psychometric qualities and has been validated and reliability tested in a variety of global demographics. The physical, mental, social, and environmental domains are the four basic areas in which the WHOQOL questionnaire evaluates quality of life. With 26 questions and a Likert scale for answer, it allows for a thorough assessment of the respondents' subjective quality of life. The questionnaire is a useful tool for clinical and research contexts, and it may be finished in around ten to fifteen minutes. Overall, the total interview time for the entire study was estimated to be 30 minutes per participant. The data collected was coded and entered, its clearing and compiling was done on a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and then it was imported into statistical packaging for social sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 for statistical analysis.

Results

The study identified psychiatric comorbidities in 65.7% of COPD patients, with varying prevalence across GOLD stages: 26.7% in GOLD1, 93.7% in GOLD2, and 100% GOLD3 [Table no. 2]. Among these comorbidities, the frequency for major depressive episode affecting 36.9% of patients was the highest, generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) 21.7%, panic disorder 17.3%, and dysthymia 3.2% [Table no. 3].

The frequency for psychiatric comorbidity in these patients increased with increasing severity of COPD [Table. No. 2,3] The analysis further revealed a decline in quality-of-life scores corresponding to increasing severity of COPD as categorized by GOLD staging. The mean scores in physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment domains were 45.14 ± 11.98 , 44.86 ± 10.86 , 49.39 ± 11.64 , and 51.10 ± 11.22 , respectively [Table no. 4]. A significant correlation was found between psychiatric comorbidity and poor quality of life ($p < 0.001$).

Table1: Mean age and duration of illness distribution with respect to psychiatric comorbidity

	Psychiatric comorbidity		t value	P value
	Absent (N=48)	Present(N=92)		
Age(Years)	52.31±9.16	59.07±8.68	-4.285	<0.001
Duration of illness	5.58±2.68	8.13±3.33	-4.577	<0.001

Table 2: Prevalence of Psychiatric comorbidity in the various stages of COPD

Psychiatric comorbidity	Gold Stages			χ^2 value	P value
	1 (N=60)	2 (N=63)	3 (N=17)		
Absent	44 (73.3%)	4 (6.3%)	0 (0.0%)	71.296	<0.001
Present	16 (26.7%)	59 (93.7%)	17 (100.0%)		

Table 3: Types of Psychiatric comorbidity distribution in the various stages of COPD [M.I.N.I]

Psychiatric comorbidity	Gold Stages			Total prevalence	χ^2 value	P-value
	1 (N=60)	2 (N=63)	3 (N=17)			
No Psychiatry	44 (73.3%)	4 (6.3%)	0 (0.0%)			
Comorbidity present				34.2%		
Major depressive episode	3 (5.0%)	25(39.7%)	6 (35.3%)	36.9%		
Major depressive						
Episode & panic disorder	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.6%)	3 (17.6%)	4.3%		
Major depressive						
episode & Generalized anxiety disorder	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.2%)	4 (23.5%)	6.5%	112.451	<0.001
Dysthymia	0 (0.0%)	2 (3.2%)	1 (5.9%)	3.2%		
Panic disorder	6 (10.0%)	9 (14.3%)	1 (5.9%)	17.3%		
Alcohol dependence & panic disorder	2 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1.4%		
Generalized anxiety disorder	3 (5.0%)	16 (25.4%)	1 (5.9%)	21.7%		
Generalized anxiety disorder & panic disorder						
Disorder & panic disorder	2 (3.3%)	4 (6.3%)	1 (5.9%)	7.6%		

Table 4: WHOQOL questionnaire findings:

WHOQOL question-naire	Psychiatric comorbidity		p-value
	Present (n=92)	Absent (n=48)	
G1	3.25	2.58	<0.001
G2	3.10	2.18	<0.001
DOMAIN 1	64.46	45.14	<0.001
DOMAIN 2	61.54	44.86	<0.001
DOMAIN 3	61.10	49.36	<0.001
DOMAIN 4	64.56	51.10	<0.001

Discussion

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a prevalent global condition, with a significant impact in India, affecting 7.4% individuals. [7] Mental illness is reported in up to 33.9% of COPD patients, contributing to increased mortality, morbidity, prolonged hospitalization, and reduced quality of life. [9] These factors are crucial in shaping the prognosis of COPD patients.

Our study enrolled 140 COPD patients, categorized by GOLD staging: GOLD1 (n=60, 42.9%), GOLD2 (n=63, 45%), and GOLD3 (n=17, 12.7%). The robust sample size provided reliable results, as similar sample sizes were used in recent studies. [10,11,12,13] The mean age of participants was 56.75±19.39 years, with the predominant age group

being 51-60 years. This skew towards older individuals could be attributed to the under diagnosis of COPD until advanced stages and the natural decline in lung function with age. In our study, patients with psychiatric comorbidities had a mean age of 59.07±8.68 years, compared to 52.31±9.16 years for those without (p<0.001). This trend aligns with studies by Chaudhary et al. and Dar SA et al., who reported similar age distributions in their COPD cohorts. [14,11]

We observed a correlation between increasing age and COPD severity, with a notable rise in psychiatric comorbidities and a decline in quality of life (p<0.001). This may be due to the cumulative effects of disease burden, physical decline, social factors, and treatment complexities. Mehta JR et al.

also reported poorer quality of life in patients at high risk (GOLD-D) compared to those at low risk (GOLD-A) ($p=0.004$)¹⁵.

Patients with psychiatric comorbidities had a mean illness duration of 8.13 ± 3.33 years, while those without had a mean duration of 5.58 ± 2.68 years ($p<0.001$). This indicates a positive correlation between longer illness duration and the presence of psychiatric comorbidities. The interplay between COPD symptoms and psychiatric symptoms can exacerbate each other, leading to worsening health outcomes and prolonged illness. Psychiatric comorbidities may also impact adherence to COPD treatment plans and lifestyle modifications.

Our study had a predominance of male participants (85.7%), with minimal female representation (14.3%). This gender disparity is likely due to higher smoking rates in males and their involvement in occupations with higher exposure to respiratory irritants. [16,17] Cultural factors also play a role in healthcare-seeking behavior and access to services. This trend was consistent with findings by Ravella et al., Chaudhary et al., and Balakrishnan & Aswath, who reported a higher proportion of male COPD patients in their studies. [12,14,10]

Educational levels among our participants showed that 40.0% lacked formal education, 38.5% had completed primary schooling, and only 6.4% had intermediate education. This trend was similar to Balakrishnan & Aswath's study, highlighting the need for targeted health messages for specific audiences to reduce COPD prevalence. [10]

Employment rates in our study were 28.5%, with 60.7% engaged in unskilled labor and 10.7% in skilled labor. The majority of patients were from rural backgrounds (85.0%), with 55.0% falling into the lower socioeconomic status bracket. This aligns with findings from Balakrishnan & Aswath and Dar SA et al., who also reported a significant number of COPD patients from rural and lower socioeconomic backgrounds. [10,11]

We observed a 72.1% prevalence of positive substance history, with 62.8% having a history of smoking and 9.2% consuming alcohol. There was a significant association between substance history and COPD severity, leading to increased psychiatric comorbidity and diminished quality of life ($p<0.05$). Smoking is a leading cause of COPD, and this trend was mirrored in studies by Chaudhary SC et al. and Dar SA et al, who found a positive correlation between smoking and COPD severity, along with an increased risk of psychiatric comorbidities. [14,11]

In our study, 65.7% of patients had psychiatric comorbidities. Within the GOLD staging, 26.7% of patients in stage 1, 93.7% in stage 2, and all patients in stage 3 exhibited psychiatric comorbidities

($p<0.001$). Balakrishnan & Aswath and Kanwar N and Chauhan reported higher prevalence rates, potentially due to their smaller sample sizes. Smaller sample sizes can introduce greater variability, leading to fluctuations in prevalence rates. [10,18]

The most common psychiatric disorder in our study was Major Depressive Episode (36.9%), followed by Generalized Anxiety Disorder (21.7%), Panic Disorder (17.3%), and Dysthymia (3.2%). These diagnoses were significantly correlated with COPD Gold Stage 2 and 3 ($p<0.05$). This aligns with findings by Gautam AK et al., Kanwar N and Chauhan N, Varghese S et al., and Negi H et al., who also reported high prevalence rates of depression in COPD cohorts. The high prevalence of depression may be due to the psychological toll of persistent breathlessness, reduced physical capacity, and social isolation. [19,18,20,21]

We found a significant decline in quality of life correlated with COPD severity ($p<0.01$). Scores for Physical Health (45.14 ± 11.98), Psychological Health (44.86 ± 10.86), Social Relationships (49.39 ± 11.64), and Environment (51.10 ± 11.22) decreased as COPD severity worsened. Lower WHOQOL scores were significantly associated with the presence of psychiatric comorbidities ($p<0.001$). These findings are consistent with prior research by Pascal OI et al., Akhtar PM et al., and Gautam AK et al., who reported deteriorating quality of life in COPD patients with psychiatric comorbidities. [22,23,19]

The diminished quality of life in COPD patients can be attributed to physiological impairments that interfere with physical activities and overall well-being. The decline in pulmonary function and physical capacity leads to functional limitations, restricting engagement in routine activities and compromising independence. This restriction also impairs social and recreational pursuits, eroding quality of life. The economic impact of COPD, including healthcare expenses and potential loss of income, adds to the burden. Societal stigma surrounding COPD further exacerbates social ostracization and emotional distress. These factors collectively form a complex web of obstacles that impede the pursuit of a fulfilling and dignified life for COPD patients.

Study Limitations: The primary limitation of this study is the small sample size and the selection of patients from a single center, which hinders the ability to make broad generalizations. Additionally, being a cross-sectional study, it has inherent limitations. Nonetheless, we believe that our research will provide valuable guidance for future studies in this field.

Conclusion

These results highlight the wide-ranging effects of

COPD, which include physical, psychological, and economic well-being in addition to respiratory health. It is essential to use a holistic therapy approach that includes patient education, psychological support, early identification, prevention, and full treatment. Healthcare policies need to lower stigma while increasing access to treatments and education, and clinicians should be on the lookout for psychiatric comorbidity. It is crucial to have access to social support, integrated care management, and regular mental health screenings. Redefining care standards and offering all-encompassing support can help individuals with COPD flourish with more energy and overall wellbeing.

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